

PROBLEMS OF OFFLINE & ONLINE SHOPPING: A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS OF PUNE CITY

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ABSTRACT

The 21st century has witnessed tremendous growth in online shopping, but it doesn't mean that customers have switched completely from offline to online shopping. Both ways of shopping have their own merits & demerits. The objective of this paper is to study the problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping. Result showed that in offline shopping Poor Replacement procedure was the major problem faced by customers followed by Insufficient Description. In online shopping Hidden Terms & Conditions was the major problem faced by customers followed by Insufficient Description. It has been concluded that there is a significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping.

Keywords: Offline Shopping, Online Shopping, Problems

INTRODUCTION:

The increase in technology provides good opportunities to the seller to reach the customer in much faster, easier and in economic way. Online shopping is emerging very fast in recent years. Now a day the internet holds the attention of retail market. Millions and millions of people shop online. On the other hand the purchasing of product from traditional market is continuing since years. Many customers go for purchasing offline so as to examine the product and hold the possession of the product just after the payment for the product. In this contemporary world customer's loyalty depends upon the consistent ability to deliver quality, value and satisfaction. Some go for offline shopping, some for online and many go for both kind of shopping. The focus of the study is on the consumer's choice to shop on internet and at the traditional stores at the

information gaining period. However online shopping is easier for the people and less price than the offline shopping. While making any purchase decision consumer should know the medium to purchase whether online shopping or the offline shopping. Consumer should decide the channel for them which can best suit to their need and wants and which can satisfy them. Even after the continuous better services from online & offline marketers, customers are encountering some problems; this paper addresses this issue only.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Using home-scan data set from Kantar Worldpanel Wang, H. H., Hao, N., Zhou, Q., Wetzstein, M. E., & Wang, Y. (2019) conducted “an empirical study on Chinese urban consumer shopping behavior from online and offline channels, using yogurt as an example. Results confirm the advantages of E-commerce relative to traditional offline retail channel in terms of keeping consumers loyal. Results also indicate the online and offline markets are of different business models, in that the online market is a separate market from offline even for the same brand. There exists evidence of brand loyalty for online shoppers but not offline. However, it is more challenging for online late entrants to build brand loyalty because consumers are price sensitive online. Firms are recommended to think of new and differentiated products online, which focus more on quality instead of price to catch the young generation with increasing income.”

Olalonpe Ige (2018) assessed “about varying kind of similarities online shopping had with conventional Non-store shopping. It discussed about factors influencing Internet shopping, the benefits, motives, and risks. In an empirical World Wide Web Survey, a number of factors were found to increase the likelihood to shop on the Internet. Previous activities in inhome shopping; computer or Internet related work; Internet; experience; active Internet use, and product uniqueness. Risk due to inability to inspect the product; payment method, and slowness of buying were found to decrease the likelihood to shop Online. One of the challenge to researchers and marketer is alike is determining the demand for online versus off line services for different classes of products, and for different types of consumers.”

Kim K.PJohnason and others (2018) examined “differences in the retail channel use of rural consumers for searching product information, and for purchasing food and fiber products between channel use groups. Multichannel shoppers rated themselves as time pressed, dissatisfied with local offerings, unattached to their community and unconcerned with financial security while shopping”

Chen, L., Gillensen, M.L. and Sherrell, D.L. (2017) assessed “utility maximization perspective based on the consumers’ preferences to use Internet for online shopping if the utility of doing so was greater than the utility of using another shopping medium. The utility derived from using a shopping channel for purchasing any product was a function of increasing as well

as decreasing or disutility attributes. An example of a utility increasing attribute of online shopping was the convenience or the benefit of having a larger choice of retailers.”

Kiely (2016) suggested that “products with a higher physical presence should provided as much sophisticated information as possible. In other words, on the Web, due to the inherent limitation in delivering sensory information, it was hard to make sound decisions for sensory products regardless of the time and effort spent on the information search. However, in the in-store environment, there was a good chance that decision quality increases if customers spent more time and effort in the information search for sensory products. It suggested that on the Website, tools for more detailed and sophisticated information would be needed for products that had such attributes. Therefore, it was interesting to see the impact of the quality of information on the customers’ dissatisfaction based on the product continuum”

Sandy Farag (2016) studied “online shopping and its relationship with In-store shopping to assess its association with behavioral and attitudinal variables of online shoppers which revealed that they made more shopping trips than non-online buyers and had a shorter shopping duration. It’s results indicated that the relationship between online buying and in-store shopping was not one of substitution but of complementarily”

OBJECTIVE:

The purposes of this research paper is to study the problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀: There is no significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

H₁: There is a significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

(a) **Research Design:** - To have a better understanding about the issue descriptive research design was used. To get the primary data close ended questionnaire was administrated.

(b) **Sample Design:** - 300 respondents were selected through stratified purposive sampling.

(c) **Analysis:** - The data collected was analyzed with the help of Arithmetic mean and t-test.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATIONS

Respondents were asked to indicate the level of problems faced by them during shopping on 5 point scale ranging from 5 (Always) to 1 (Never). Final ranking is obtained with the help of arithmetic mean. The analysis of results is presented in further sub sections.

1. Problems Faced by Respondents during Offline Shopping

Customers indicated various problems faced by them during offline shopping as presented in table 1. Result shows that Poor Replacement procedure was the major problem faced by customers with a weighted mean score of 2.99 followed by Insufficient Description (Weighted Mean score = 2.94). Non-availability of desired products ranked 3rd with a Weighted Mean score of 2.92, followed by Unavailability of discounts & offers that ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 2.80. Unavailability of door delivery ranked as fifth problem with weighted mean score of 2.79 tailed by Retailer’s Behavior at 6th rank with a weighted mean score of 2.77.

The moderate level of problems ranked from 7th to 10th position respectively were Poor Packaging (Weighted Mean score = 2.58), Lack of credit facility (Weighted Mean score = 2.50), Damaged Product (Weighted Mean score = 2.32) and Difficulty in payment options (Weighted Mean score = 2.07).

Table 1: Problems Faced by Respondents during Offline Shopping

Weights	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Weighted Total	Weighted Avg.	Rank
Level of Problems	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Always				
Problems									
Insufficient Description	8	78	137	77	0	300	883	2.94	2
Retailer’s Behavior	8	116	114	62	0	300	830	2.77	6
Damaged Product	48	108	144	0	0	300	696	2.32	9
Poor Replacement procedure	8	97	125	31	39	300	896	2.99	1
Difficulty in payment options	66	162	56	16	0	300	622	2.07	10
Non-availability of desired products	16	98	79	107	0	300	877	2.92	3
Unavailability of door delivery	16	63	190	31	0	300	836	2.79	5
Lack of credit facility	39	112	110	39	0	300	749	2.50	8
Unavailability of discounts & offers	16	83	146	55	0	300	840	2.80	4
Poor Packaging	68	45	140	39	8	300	774	2.58	7

Table 2 is presenting the overall Level of Problems Faced by Respondents during Offline Shopping. Majority of respondents (N=163, Percentage=54.3) said that they sometimes faced the problem followed by 35% respondents (N=105) who seldom faced the problems. Equal number of respondents (N=16, Percentage=5.3) indicated they either they often faced the problems or they never faced the problems during offline shopping. As per the mean score (26.68) respondents sometimes faced the problems during offline shopping.

Table 2: Overall Level of Problems Faced by Respondents during Offline Shopping

Level of Problems Faced	N	Percentage
Never	16	5.3
Seldom	105	35.0
Sometimes	163	54.3
Often	16	5.3
Always	0	0.0
Total	300	100
Mean Score	26.68	
Result	Sometimes	

2. Problems Faced by Respondents during Online Shopping

Respondents indicated various problems faced by them during online shopping on five point scale 5 (Always) to 1 (Never) as presented in table 3. Result shows that Hidden Terms & Conditions was the major problem faced by customers with a weighted mean score of 3.14 followed by Insufficient Description (Weighted Mean score = 2.84). Poor Response of Customer Care ranked 3rd with a Weighted Mean score of 2.81, followed by High delivery charges that ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 2.72. Delay in delivery ranked as fifth problem with weighted mean score of 2.68 tailed by Poor Replacement procedure at 6th rank with a weighted mean score of 2.66.

The moderate level of problems ranked from 7th to 11th position respectively were Damaged Product (Weighted Mean score = 2.51), Poor Packaging (Weighted Mean score = 2.37), Lack of Personalized Services (Weighted Mean score = 2.33), Color Variation (Weighted Mean score = 2.26) and Difficulty in payment options (Weighted Mean score = 1.92).

Table 3: Problems Faced by Respondents during Online Shopping

Weights	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Weighted Total	Weighted Avg.	Rank
Level of Problems	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Always				
Problems									
Insufficient Description	39	54	138	55	14	300	851	2.84	2
Delay in delivery	14	93	169	24	0	300	803	2.68	5
Damaged Product	8	139	145	8	0	300	753	2.51	7
Poor Replacement procedure	12	148	71	67	2	300	799	2.66	6
Difficulty in payment options	93	153	40	14	0	300	575	1.92	11
Color Variation	45	150	57	27	11	290	679	2.26	10
High delivery charges	16	93	161	18	12	300	817	2.72	4
Hidden Terms & Conditions	8	85	118	35	54	300	942	3.14	1
Poor Response of Customer Care	31	62	154	39	14	300	843	2.81	3
Poor Packaging	45	147	70	28	10	300	711	2.37	8
Lack of Personalized Services	45	147	75	29	4	300	700	2.33	9

Table 4 is presenting the overall Level of Problems Faced by Respondents during Online Shopping. Majority of respondents (N=138, Percentage=46) said that they sometimes faced the problem followed by 31% respondents (N=93) who seldom faced the problems. Rest of the respondents indicated they either they often faced the problems or they never faced the problems during offline shopping. As per the mean score (26.94) respondents seldom faced the problems during offline shopping.

Table 4: Overall Level of Problems Faced by Respondents during Online Shopping

Level of Problems Faced	N	Percentage
Never	45	15.0
Seldom	93	31.0
Sometimes	138	46.0
Often	24	8.0
Always	0	0.0
Total	300	100
Mean Score	26.94	
Result	Seldom	

3. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₀: There is no significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

H₁: There is a significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

To measure the significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping, t-test is used and results received are presented in table 5.

Table 5: t-test result to measure significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

Factor		Mean	S.D.	t-values	P-value	Result
Problems Faced	Offline	26.68	5.197	51.728	0.00	Significant
	Online	26.94	8.325			

sLevel of Significance = 5%

The p-value signifies that the t-statistic is significant which means that null hypothesis holds to be false and it can be inferred that there is a significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

CONCLUSION:

From this research following conclusions can be drawn:-

1. Result showed that in offline shopping Poor Replacement procedure was the major problem faced by customers followed by Insufficient Description.
2. In online shopping Hidden Terms & Conditions was the major problem faced by customers followed by Insufficient Description.
3. There is a significant difference between problems faced by consumers during online & offline shopping

REFERENCES:

- Chen, L., Gillensen, M.L. And Sherrell, D.L. (2017); *“Consumer Acceptance Of Virtual Stores: A Theoretical Model And Critical Success Factors For Virtual Stores”*; ACM SIGMIS; Vol. 35 ;No. 2; PP.34-45.
- Kiely, T. (2016); *“The Pleasures And Perils Of Selling In Cyberspace”*, Insights From Marketing Science Institute; Winter/Spring 2016.
- Kim K.P.Johanson, Jeong Ju Yoo, Jongeun Rhee, Sharron Lenno, Cynthia Jasper And Mary Lynn Damhorst (2018); *“Multi Channel Shopping: Channel Use Among Rural Consumers”*; International Journal O Retail And Distribution Management; Vol.34; No.6; PP.453-466.
- Olalonpe Ige (2018); *“Electronic Shopping: Young People As Consumers”*; International Journal Of Consumer Studies; Vol.28, No.4; 2004; PP.412-427.

Sandy Farag And Others (2016); *“E-Shopping And Its Relationship With In Store Shopping: Empirical Evidence From The Netherlands And USA”*; Transport Reviews; Vol.26; No. 1; 2006; PP. 43-61.

Wang, H. H., Hao, N., Zhou, Q., Wetzstein, M. E., & Wang, Y. (2019). *“Is fresh food shopping sticky to retail channels and online platforms? Evidence and implications in the digital era.”* Agribusiness, 35(1), 6-19